

THE EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE MIXED-MODE INTERLAMINAR TOUGHNESS AND FATIGUE DELAMINATION GROWTH OF FRPs

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Abstract:

This paper addresses the characterisation of the effect of temperature on the fracture toughness and the fatigue delamination growth rate for a carbon fibre-reinforced and thermoplastic-toughened epoxy, namely IM7/8552. All tests have been performed using asymmetric cut-ply specimens subjected to four-point bending at temperatures ranging from -50°C to 80°C. We show that the mixed-mode fracture toughness is increased at 80°C with respect to the other test conditions. Moreover, raising the temperature delays the fatigue delamination growth at relatively high severities. On the other hand, at low severities, i.e. in the near threshold regime, increasing temperatures accelerate the delamination growth.

1. Introduction

Fibre-reinforced composites offer a lightweight solution for primary structures due to their excellent in-plane mechanical properties. However fibre-reinforced composites are prone to accumulate interlaminar damage in the form of progressive delamination. Interlaminar stress risers, such as ply drop-off and free-edges, are intrinsic features of composite structures. Their impact on the material performance can be limited by a careful damage tolerance design, albeit not completely suppressed [1]. Delaminations are usually initiated at locations where significant interlaminar stresses are attained and they tend to grow under fatigue loading. Therefore, robust physical models that capture both the initiation and propagation of delaminations are needed for the damage tolerant design of composite structures. These models should include the effects of environmental conditions on the durability of fibre-reinforced composites.

Fatigue delamination propagation in fibre-reinforced composites is usually described via a power law relating the delamination growth rate (DGR) to the energy release rate (ERR) attained at the interlaminar crack tip. This power law is commonly denoted as “Paris equation”. However, due to the visco-elastic nature of the matrix, the temperature affects the characteristic pre-factor and the exponent that appear in the Paris law. The effect of temperature is significant also below the matrix glass transition temperature. Similar considerations hold true for the effect of moisture. Albeit the effects of temperature and moisture on the fatigue delamination growth in composites have been documented in the literature [2-12], there is still no general consensus about their trends and magnitude. This issue is exacerbated by the fact that the formulation of material systems is being constantly upgraded in order to improve the interlaminar fracture toughness. However, the main driver of such developments is the room temperature performance. This does not necessarily translate into better fatigue damage tolerance, especially when environmental effects are taken into account.

In this paper, we characterise the static toughness and fatigue delamination growth of a “second generation” fibre-reinforced toughened epoxy, namely IM7/8552. We consider a temperature range from -50°C to 80°C. Asymmetric cut-ply specimens (ACP) [15] subjected to four point bending are employed. The specimens consist of unidirectional (UD) laminates having constant thickness, with some of the plies cut in the middle of the gauge section, as described by Lander et al. [15]. Two symmetric delaminations are emanated from the cut and they propagate along the interface that corresponds to the depth of the cut. For the ACP

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tests, the mode mixity at the delamination crack front remains constant during crack propagation and can be adjusted by altering the ratio of the number of cut plies to the total number of plies.

We demonstrate that the static interlaminar fracture toughness increases at the highest temperature considered in our tests. However, we also show that an increase in temperature accelerates the delamination growth at low severities, i.e. in the near threshold regime. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) fractography is employed to characterize the effect of temperature on the delamination surfaces, both in static and fatigue conditions.

2. Analytical Methodology

2.1 Asymmetric Cut Ply Specimens (ACP)

A sketch of the ACP configuration is presented in fig. 1. The specimen comprises a mid-section cut, which extends from the top surface to a prescribed depth t_1 . By definition χ is the ratio of the cut depth to the overall specimen thickness $t = t_1 + t_2$. For plies having constant thickness, χ is simply the ratio of the number of cut plies to the total number of plies. The ACP test does not require any compliance calibration in order to measure the delamination length. This represent a major advantage with respect to other methods of mixed-mode fatigue testing, such as the “mixed-mode bending” MMB coupon configuration [13-14].

In order to promote delamination, a PTFE film having a total length $2a$ is inserted symmetrically beneath the cut. In this paper, it is considered that the ply thickness is constant with a ratio of cut to continuous plies of 0.5, which corresponds to a mode-mixity of 0.43.

2.2 Energy Release Rate (ERR) Determination

The delamination-tip ERR in ACP specimens is independent from the crack length. Following the procedure outlined in ref. [15], the mode I G_I and mode II G_{II} ERR for the ACP specimen are given by:

$$G_I = \frac{6M^2}{K^*Et^3} \frac{\psi}{\chi^3 + (1 - \chi)^3} \quad (1)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{6M^2}{K^*Et^3} \left[\frac{1}{\chi^3 + (1 - \chi)^3} - 1 \right] \quad (2)$$

Where E is the material longitudinal Young’s modulus, M is the applied bending moment and ψ is given by:

$$\psi = \frac{\chi^3}{(1 - \chi)^3} \quad (3)$$

In order to correct for the actual initial delamination length associated to each individual sample, a calibration coefficient K^* is introduced. This is the ratio of the peak applied bending moment during testing, over the theoretical bending moment (M_0) for the assumed initial delamination length $\alpha_0 = 10\text{mm}$.

$$K^* = \frac{\hat{M}}{M_0} \quad (4)$$

Where

$$M_0 = \frac{\beta EI}{L + \alpha_0 \left[\frac{1 - (1 - \chi)^3}{(1 - \chi)^3} \right]} \quad (5)$$

The total ERR (G) is given by adding eqs. (1) and (2) and it has the following expression:

$$G = \frac{6M^2}{K^*Et^3} \left[\frac{1}{(1 - \chi)^3} - 1 \right] \quad (6)$$

The mode-mixity is given by

$$\varphi = \frac{G_{II}}{G} = \frac{3(1 - \chi)^4}{(1 - 3\chi + 3\chi^2)(3 - 3\chi + \chi^2)} \quad (7)$$

From eqs. (1)-(7) one can immediately observe that, given a constant applied bending moment M , the ERR in ACP specimens is independent from the crack length and so is the mode-mixity. Actually, the latter depends only on the thickness ratio χ , as it has been mentioned above. If χ is small, then $\varphi \rightarrow 1$, i.e. a pure mode II regime is approached. On the other hand, for $\chi \rightarrow 1$ one finds $\varphi \rightarrow 0$, so the delamination tends to grow in mode I dominated conditions.

Clearly, there are practical limitations on the range of χ , because cutting a large number of plies would make the specimen extremely compliant. Similarly, in order to approximate mode II it is necessary to make the specimen relatively thick, which invalidates the assumption of zero through thickness shear strains on which the ERR and mode-mixity expressions are based [15].

2.3 Large rotation correction

Since the ACP specimen is relatively thin and subjected to four-point bending, large rotations can occur at the end tabs. This implies that the relation between the bending moment M acting at the delamination tip and the applied force needs to account for such large rotations.

As demonstrated in fig. 2, due to the rotation angle β the actual force applied by the roller onto the specimen is given by:

$$F = \frac{P}{2\cos\beta} \quad (8)$$

Where P is the peak applied load. On the other hand, the arm between the applied force on the loading roller and the reaction force on the static roller is given by:

$$\mu = \frac{d_x}{\cos\beta} - (D + t_T)\tan\beta \quad (9)$$

Where D is the roller diameter and t_T is the thickness of the tabbed region.

2.4 Bending moment correction and coefficient of friction

The actual bending moment per unit width applied during the test is a function of the specimen rotation between the rollers. Grooved rollers were employed in order to avoid the specimen slipping in the jig during the fatigue tests. However, in the static tests it was observed that the grooved rollers produced an increase of the bending moment to failure with respect to the cases where smooth supports were employed.

This was due to the friction of the roller. This effect was included in the bending moment calculations, and the associated formula was corrected as follows:

$$M = \frac{P}{2W\cos\beta} [\mu - \varpi t_T] \quad (10)$$

Where ϖ is the roller coefficient of friction. This can be determined comparing the slopes of the bending moment curves prior to failure for the smooth and grooved supports. Substituting μ from eq. (9) into eq. (10), the corrected bending moment is given by:

$$M = \frac{P}{2W\cos\beta} \left\{ \frac{d_x}{\cos\beta} - (D + t_T)\tan\beta - \varpi t_T \right\} \quad (11)$$

Where W is the averaged specimen width.

Assuming the bending and shear deformations in the tabbed area of the specimen are negligible; it is possible to estimate the specimen rotation by means of the cross-head displacement c only. This leads to the following equation:

$$\tan\beta = \frac{c - (D + t_T)(1 - \cos\beta)}{d_x - (D + t_T)\sin\beta} \quad (12)$$

This has to be solved iteratively. Substituting the solution of eq. (12) into eq. (11) for a given load cell force P and cross-head displacement c , yields the corrected applied bending moment M .

2.5 Estimation of delamination length and growth rates

Considering that fatigue delamination growth tests are carried out in a displacement controlled regime, it is possible to derive the delamination growth rates directly from the cross-head displacement and load-cell force readings, provided that the loading jig is sufficiently stiff under fatigue and the compliance of the machine is negligible.

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Let a sinusoidal load be applied to the specimen. The deformed shape of the specimen under loading is described by the following equations:

$$\frac{d\hat{\theta}}{ds} = \begin{cases} \frac{\hat{M}W}{EI(1-\chi^3)} & 0 \leq s \leq a \\ \frac{\hat{M}W}{EI} & a < s \leq L \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Where, as shown in fig. 3, $\hat{\theta}(s)$ is the rotation of the beam section and s is a curvilinear abscissa defined along the deformed beam axis, a is the delamination length, \hat{M} is the peak applied bending moment and $I=1/12Wt^3$ is the cross-sectional second moment of area. Let θ^* be the specimen rotation at the delamination tip position $s=a$ corresponding to the peak bending moment. Note that the rotation at the mid-plane, i.e. for $s=0$ is zero, while the rotation at the loading roller, i.e. $s=L$, is $\hat{\beta}$ given by eq. (12) solved for the peak cross-head displacement \hat{c} during the fatigue cycle.

In principle, any point during the fatigue cycle could be considered for the crack length measurement, but at the peak bending moment the force applied by the machine is maximum and so the load-cell measurement is less prone to linearity errors. It should also be observed that there will always be a delay between the time at which the peak force is applied and that for maximum displacement. This is due to the inherent damping in the specimen, so care must be taken in recording the correct peak force and displacement values.

Integrating eq. (13) one gets:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta^* &= \frac{\hat{M}W}{EI(1-\chi^3)} \\ \hat{\beta} - \theta^* &= \frac{\hat{M}W}{EI} (L - a) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Combining eqs. (14) and solving with respect to the crack length yields:

$$\begin{aligned} a &= k_{(\chi)} \left[\frac{\hat{\beta}EI}{\hat{M}W} - L \right] \\ k_{(\chi)} &= \frac{(1-\chi)^3}{1-(1-\chi)^3} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Since all tests run in a displacement control regime, i.e. for a constant peak cross head displacement (\hat{c}), $\hat{\beta}$ is constant in eqs. (14-15) by virtue of eq. (12).

Thus for the crack growth rate measured in a displacement controlled test one has:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = -k_{(\chi)} \frac{\hat{\beta}EI}{W\hat{M}^2} \frac{d\hat{M}}{dN} \quad (16)$$

Note that in eq. (16) the peak bending moment decreases with the number of load cycles, since the crack length increases and so does the specimen compliance. This proves that using ACP specimens it is possible to measure the FDGR during a fatigue test by means of the load-cell readings and the cross-head displacements alone.

3 Experimental Testing

3.1 Specimen manufacturing

Unidirectional ACP specimens were manufactured using Hexcel® IM7/8552 carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy. The specimens comprised ten plies, out of which five were cut, giving $\chi=1/2$. The nominal cured ply thickness for IM7/8552 is 0.127 mm, giving a total specimen nominal thickness of 1.27 mm. The actual thickness measured on the coupons was within 2% the nominal value. Unidirectional IM7/8552 has a Young's modulus $E = 161$ GPa.

The total specimen length was 190 mm, with a gauge section of $2L = 90$ mm and a width $W = 15$ mm. The tabbed areas extended for 50 mm at both ends of the gauge section. The tabs were manufactured using E-Glass/Epoxy 950 pre-preg material arranged in a cross-ply stacking. The manufacturing process of the samples consisted of the lay-up and vacuum consolidation of two initially individual ply-stacks made of 5 plies each. One of the two stacks had been cut in half. A 20mm long,

12.7 μ m thick and 15mm wide Teflon® PTFE film was embedded at the centre of the first ply-stack and subsequently covered with the second ply-stack. Thus the film inserts simulates the presence of an initial delamination $2a = 20$ mm long. The two halves of the cut stack were tightly pushed together along the cut line, so no central gap is formed. The full laminate was de-bulked in vacuum at room temperature for 20 minutes and then cured in the autoclave. The tabs were then bonded to the specimens using the Redux® 810 bi-component epoxy adhesive. The total thickness of the specimen in the tabbed areas was 6.4 mm.

After curing, it was observed that a vertical resin bridge had formed at the cut location, joining the two laminate halves and preventing the delamination from opening. The resin join was fractured applying a low level of tension to the specimen, taking care that, in the meanwhile, no delamination propagation occurred. The specimens were kept in desiccator cabinet before testing.

In the literature it is reported that artificial delaminations created by the insertion of thin films may affect the measured value of the fracture toughness. O'Brien [17] considered ENF specimens with PTFE film inserts having the same thickness with the ones considered here. He carried out static fracture tests both by growing the delamination directly from the insert and pre-cracking the coupons by applying fatigue cycles before the static tests. He reported that the mode II fracture toughness of IM7/8552 was 50% higher for non-pre-cracked (NPC) ENF coupons compared with pre-cracked (PC) ENF specimens. Thus growing delamination directly from the film insert may lead to an overestimation of the actual material fracture toughness. Such effect is likely due to the fact that the delamination tip for NPC specimens is blunted by the presence of the insert, thus increasing the measured fracture toughness of the material with respect to PC coupons, for which the crack front is sharp.

In order to take into account the possible enhancement of the mixed-mode fracture toughness due to the presence of the thin films, NPC and PC specimens are also considered here for the room temperature tests. The pre-cracking was carried out by symmetrically clamping the specimen with metal

blocks at a set distance of 20mm from the central cut. A force was applied at the cut location on the face opposite to the cut itself until the delamination had symmetrically grown to the inner edges of the clamping blocks. The procedure was repeated until both sides of the specimen propagated the same amount. C-scans were performed after the pre-cracking in order to check that the position of the delamination front was uniform across the specimen width. A sample of the C-scans is presented in fig. 4.

3.2 Experimental Procedure

The four-point bending tests were carried out using a jig with roller distance $d_x = 25$ mm. The loading jig is shown in fig. 5. It comprises a long push rod in order to be used within an environmental chamber for testing at variable temperature. For the low temperature testing at -50°C , the environmental chamber was filled with CO_2 gas supplied by a liquid CO_2 vessel. In order to avoid any slippage of the specimens at low temperature, anti-icing liquid was used to ensure that no ice was formed between the loading rollers and the coupons. The temperature in the chamber and specimen was controlled throughout the testing. The correct positioning of the sample within the test rig is of crucial importance for the test accuracy. Therefore an alignment tool was manufactured to ensure that the cut position was exactly in between the loading rollers. The static fracture toughness was determined for NPC and PC coupons at room temperature, i.e. 20°C , -50°C , 50°C and 80°C . At least three specimens were tested in each case.

The fatigue tests were run in displacement control, starting from a displacement corresponding to 70% of the static strength, with a constant stress ratio $R = 0.1$. Again four temperatures were considered, namely -50°C , 20°C , 50°C and 80°C . Each test was performed using a sinusoidal displacement input with a frequency of 5 Hz and for a total 10^6 cycles.

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Static Tests

The static tests for the characterisation of the fracture toughness were carried out in displacement control mode. A selection of bending moment versus cross-head displacement curves recorded during the tests are presented in fig. 6-8 for the NPC cases,

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while a summary of the fracture toughness values obtained is given in table. 1. The bending moment was calculated from the individual load-displacement curves using the large rotation correction presented in sec. 2.3.

From the NPC tests carried out at 20°C and presented in fig. 6, one can observe that the applied bending moment increases almost linearly until an average peak bending moment value of 45 N is reached at an average displacement of 5.8 mm. This marks the onset of static delamination growth. Note that the bending moment is here given per unit width. Further increasing the displacement beyond the delamination onset threshold leads to a bending moment plateau, corresponding to an observed stable symmetric delamination growth with respect to the central cut. Crack propagation is found to be stable up to an average crosshead displacement of 10mm.

Inserting the experimental value of the bending moment for delamination propagation into eq. (6) allows calculating the material mixed-mode fracture toughness. The load-displacement curves for the tests carried out on PC specimens at room temperature followed exactly the same trend observed for the NPC specimens and the associated bending moment for delamination growth show no statistically significant difference from that obtained for the NPC coupons. Thus only the NPC values are reported in table. 1. The pre-cracking does not have a significant effect on the measured toughness values at any temperature.

Increasing the temperature has a notable impact on the way delamination propagate under static loading. Due to the use of grooved rollers, “stick-slip” behaviour was observed even at room temperature conditions. In the “stick-slip” regime, reloading phases followed sudden increments of delamination length. In some cases, the recorded load appeared to increase steadily after the initiation point, giving a local peak value well after initiation. It was observed that the extent of the symmetric propagation plateau region at 50°C was slightly smaller than at 20°C. The region where the bending moment appears to drop is that of asymmetric delamination growth, where the formulas given in eqs. (1, 2, 6) and (10, 11) are not applicable any more. As the temperature increases further, the “stick slip” behaviour for the

specimens tested with grooved rollers becomes stronger as can be seen in fig. 6-7.

Interestingly, strong “stick-slip” behaviour was observed also at -50°C as can be seen in fig. 8.

For the calculation of the ERR according to eqs. (1, 2, 6) and (10, 11) symmetric delamination growth is required. Therefore the ERR calculation was carried out considering only the portions of the load-displacement curves where equal interlaminar crack lengths with respect to the central cut were actually observed.

A summary of the toughness values calculated from the tests is presented in table. 1. For temperatures ranging from -50°C to 50°C, no significant variation of the fracture toughness was observed. However, at 80°C the fracture toughness was found to be approximately 39% higher in comparison to the one measured at room temperature.

4.2 Fatigue Tests

During the fatigue tests, the crosshead displacements and load cell force were recorded every five cycles. Eq. (16) allows computing the delamination growth rate directly from such data. The delamination growth observed during the tests was generally stable, with the noteworthy exception of the first few hundred cycles. In these cases the crack initially propagated very fast, i.e. at about 10^{-2} mm/cycle, exhibiting asymmetric length increments with respect to the central cut. This “stick-slip” propagation mechanism at relatively large applied loading was analogous to that observed during the static tests, albeit less severe. When the delamination reached a length of approximately 15 mm with respect to central cut, the further growth occurred symmetrically with respect to the central cut and the “stick-slip” behaviour disappeared.

The data reduction technique described in the ASTM E647 standard [18] was adapted to estimate the delamination growth rates from the experimental bending moment data. This is based on a multi-point quadratic interpolation method.

A summary of the results of the fatigue tests is presented in fig. 9. Here the FDGR are plotted against the peak ERR (\hat{G}) applied during the test normalised with respect to the fracture toughness at

the corresponding temperature. From fig. 9 one can observe that the fatigue delamination growth tends to increase with temperature, especially for the lower severities, i.e. in the near threshold regime. This effect is extremely important from an engineering design point of view, since the near threshold regime is that usually considered for the damage tolerance design of composite structural elements. Fig. 9 proves that an increase in static fracture toughness does not necessarily correspond to a better performance in fatigue.

5. SEM Fractography

The fractographic analysis of coupons reveals no major morphological differences between static and fatigue grown delaminations. In general the specimens tested statically have rougher surfaces compared to those tested in fatigue. Some minor differences include, for the fatigue case, reduced bridging and the appearance of small matrix “rollers”, which are aligned almost perpendicularly to the fibre direction. At room temperature, the SEM images for static and fatigue samples show a small amount of fibre bridging apparent from the broken fibres (fig. 10 a), with partly developed shear cusps in the intra-fibre spacing. At higher magnifications, small resin granules dispersed in the fracture surface can be observed. The surfaces exposed at higher temperatures display a similar morphology, albeit slightly rougher and with more developed shear cusps. In the fatigue samples, one can also observe more surface debris. Nonetheless, bridging fibres and bare fibres appear in larger number at both low and high temperatures with respect to the room temperature case. This may be to the mismatch of thermal expansion coefficients between the fibres and the matrix.

6 Conclusions

The mixed-mode fracture toughness of IM7/8552 has been characterized using ACP specimens. In this study four testing temperatures have been considered, namely -50°C, 20°C, 50°C and 80°C. An increase of the fracture toughness was observed at 80°C with respect to the room temperature case. No significant variation of fracture toughness was highlighted between -50°C and 50°C. The increase in fracture toughness at elevated temperatures is accompanied by more pronounced “stick-slip” behaviour during delamination growth. No

statistically significant differences in fracture toughness were observed when growing the delamination directly from the insert film with respect to pre-cracking the specimens.

The toughness enhancement with temperature does not correspond to smaller fatigue DGR for the same normalised ERR. Actually, an increase in temperature accelerates delamination growth, especially in the near threshold regime. This effect may have important consequences for the design of aerospace structures, since these are sized and certified according to a “no growth” criterion for delaminations.

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of the ACP specimens, under four point bending.

Fig. 2: Specimen rotations and associated forces at the rollers.

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Fig. 3: Specimen deformed configuration.

Fig. 4: C-scans of pre-cracked specimens.

Fig. 5: 4-point loading jig employed for the static and fatigue tests

Fig. 6: Bending moment vs. displacement curve for NPC specimens at 20°C using grooved rollers.

Fig. 7: Bending moment vs. displacement curve for NPC specimen at 80°C using grooved rollers.

Fig. 8: Bending moment vs. displacement curve for NPC specimen at -50°C using grooved rollers.

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Fig. 9: DGD versus normalised ERR curves at various temperature conditions. The shift of the data in regards to the reference room temperature is illustrated for each graph along with the best-fit modified Paris Law equation that accounts the effect of temperature, presented with a dashed line. The chart at bottom left hand corner shows a comparison of the DGR data gathered at room temperature using ACP specimens with data from a more conventional MMB test [19].

Fig. 10: Micrograph of a specimen exposed to fatigue loading at: a) room temperature and b) 80°C (800x magnification).

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Table 1: Experimental mixed-mode fracture toughness for IM7/8552; $\phi=0.43$

	-50°C	20°C	50°C	80°C
G_c (kJ/m ²)	0.30 (3) ^(a)	0.28 (3) ^(a)	0.29 (3) ^(a)	0.39 (3) ^(a)
<i>Grooved*</i>	(0.04) ^(b)	(0.02) ^(b)	(0.03) ^(b)	(0.03) ^(b)
	(a) Number of specimens tested (b) Standard deviation of the fracture toughness *Refers to roller configuration			

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